

THE EFFECT OF COMPLEX MULTI-MODALITY AYURVEDA TREATMENT OF *UTTARA BASTI* (TRANS-URETHRAL ADMINISTRATION) WITH *SHATAVARI GHRITA* UNDERGOING IUI IN SECONDARY FEMALE INFERTILITY: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Infertility refers to the inability to achieve a successful pregnancy after continuous, unprotected intercourse for more than 12 months. It has now been declared as one of the most significant global health concerns and has shown to affect the patient both mentally and emotionally. The treatment has been growing globally and despite improvements in medical strategies, Ayurveda has various treatment modalities to treat the conditions. Female infertility has many etiological factors, however, mainly endometrial factors and cervical factors play a vital role. Ayurveda emphasizes achieving a normal pregnancy through the maintenance of *Garbha Samgraha Samagri* and mental equilibrium. **Aim:** To evaluate the *Prajasthapana* effect of *Uttara Basti* with *Shatavari Ghritha* prior to IUI in the management of female infertility. **Methodology:** A 34-year-old female with a healthy

and normal sexual life came with the complaints of infertility. The patient was administered *uttara basti* in morning evening pattern and when the follicle size reaches >18mm, In Uterine Fertilization was carried out for 3 consecutive days. **Results:** Statistical analysis revealed that the endometrial thickness and cervical mucus improved after administration of course of

Niruha and *Uttara Basti*. **Conclusion:** Integration of treatment protocol of ayurveda with modern protocols is the key factor in successful fertility has the potential to improvement of patient outcome.

KEYWORDS: Uttar Basti, Prajasthapana, Secondary Infertility, Infertility, endometriosis, IUI.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines infertility as the inability of a sexually active, non-contraceptive couple to achieve pregnancy for more than 12 months.^[1] There has been a rapid change and advancement in technology but infertility remains the burning issue worldwide and currently, around 17% of couples in industrialized countries get treatment for infertility.^[2] Primary and secondary infertility are two types commonly found in females. Various factors can cause infertility however among these endometrial factors and cervical factors play an important role.^[3] The main factors for progression for pregnancy are implantation and conception and implantation failures are diverse and different maternal factors such as hormonal, uterine abnormalities contribute to the implantation and conception.

Furthermore, the endometrial is said as the dynamic inner muscular lining of the uterus which overall responds to the hormonal changes of the ovarian cycle and sheds cyclically, and provides a favorable physiological environment for embryo implantation.^[4] As per *ayurveda*, infertility is defined as *vandhya*, which means not being able to conceive. *Ayurveda*, states that conception is the result of healthy sperm, healthy ovum, and a healthy uterus.^[5] Thus implantation can be understood as *prajasthapana*. Intrauterine insemination (IUI) has many indications and it helps to bypass the hostile factors and increase the chances of conception.^[6] The success of IUI depends on performing the insemination at the time of ovulation.^[7] The main ingredient *shatavari* is one of the *prajasthapana* *dravya* and possesses the estrogenic and anti abortifacient property that enhance the quality of endometrium and thus increase chances of conception.^[8] *Uttara Basti* gives desirable therapeutic drug concentration at the site of action. Thus it is considered the best mode of administration of a drug for the *yonigata rogas* including *vandhya*.

CASE PRESENTATION

Patient Background

A 34 year - old female with a healthy and normal sexual life came with complaints of infertility for 2 years. The patient was said to be healthy two years back but gradually developed hair fall and itching sensations in the scalp region. Her menstrual was regular and no whitish discharge was noted. Furthermore, the patient tried conceiving naturally for the first time where the conception took place however miscarriage happened. The patient tried to conceive once again but was not able to conceive. The patient had no history of the use of contraception, besides her infertility complaints, the patient was healthy. The patient approached infertility centers where she was advised oral medications and in vitro fertilization however due to unavailability of satisfactory treatment and failing to get any response from allopathic treatment, the patient decided to take *Ayurvedic* treatment. Patient was diagnosed with *vandhya* (Secondary Infertility) and *panchakarma* procedures were planned accordingly. Her husband's semen analysis was normal and no particular defect was found in the semen analysis.

Clinical findings

On clinical examinations revealed loss of hair and dry course skin. All her systemic examinations were clear and no pathological issues were found. A routine gynecological examination showed normal reproductive system. However, a routine abdomen ultra sound was suggested and there were no significant pathology found. The uterus was normal in size and showed homogeneous echo texture with no evidence of fibroids. The ovaries were healthy and normal in size. Patient was again advised Trans-vaginal USG Pelvis in which uterus was normal in size measuring 5.0 x 2.7 x 3.7cms and endometrial thickness measure 11.00mm. Follicular study was also done.

Diagnostic Assessment

The patient was diagnosed with PCOD induced secondary infertility. After thorough clinical examinations, the condition matched with signs and symptoms of *rajovaha sroto dusti* and was diagnosed with *vandhyatwa*. Observations were done parameter like cervical mucus quality and were assessed on the 1st and last day of IUI, endometrial thickness was also assessed on the first and last day of IUI.

Therapeutic Intervention

The aim of the intervention was to appreciate the effect of *uttara basti* in female infertility. Furthermore, *Uttara basti* and IUI was carried as per the standard operative procedure including counseling of the patient.

Table No. 1: Treatment Protocol for *Uttar Basti*.

Days of MC		6 th day	7 th day	8 th day	9 th day	10 th Day
Type of Basti	Morning	-	Niruha Basti	Niruha Basti	Niruha Basti	-
	Evening	Anuvasana Basti	Uttara Basti	Uttara Basti	Uttara Basti	Anuvasana Basti

Balaguduchiyadi niruha basti (Enema) was planned followed by *anuvasa basti* with *shatavari ghrta (Asparagus racemosus)*. The contents are mentioned in Table no 2.

SI NO	Content	Quantity
1.	Honey	60ml
2.	<i>Saindhava Lavana (Potassium Cholride)</i>	5gms
3.	<i>Sneha (Oil) (Balaguduchiyadi Taila)</i>	100ml
4.	<i>Kalka (Fine Powder Paste)(Putiyavani Kalka)</i>	40gms
5.	<i>Kashaya (Decoction) (Balaguduchiyadi)</i>	250ml

Visit and Follow Up

There were total of five follows by the patients with oral medications. (Table no 3).

Si NO	Days	Medicine with Dosage
1	15 Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cap Ovarian 1TID • Kanchanara Gugglu 1TID • Mushilikhadiradi Khashaya 3tsf BD
2	15 Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cap Ovarian 1TID ▪ Kanchanara Gugglu 1TID ▪ Arogyavartini Vati 1TID ▪ Cap Gynocare 2TID
3	15 Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cap Ovarian 1TID • Kanchanara Gugglu 1TID • Arogyavartini Vati 1TID • Ashoka Arista 3tsf TID • Rajapravartini Vati 2TID
4	15 Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cap Ovarian 1TID • Kanchanara Gugglu 1TID • Arogyavartini Vati 1TID • Ashoka Arista 3tsf TID • Rajapravartini Vati 2TID • Sapthasara Kashaya 3tsf BD
5	15 Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cap Ovarian 1TID • Kanchanara Gugglu 1TID • Arogyavartini Vati 1TID

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ashoka Arista 3tsf TID Rajapravartini Vati 2TID
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Intervention adherence and tolerability

The patient signed consent and with her own will and opted to take *ayurveda* treatment. The patient was engrossed to take *Uttara Basti* to improve her current condition and help her fertility to get a healthy progeny.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

Table No. 4: Results Obtained after treatment.

Factors	Patient A (Before)
Marital Life	2 Years
H/O Abortion	No
Treatment H/O IUI	No
Family History	No
BMI	21.33
Endometrial thickness	
Baseline on 12th day	7mm
Treatment cycle on 12th day	6mm
Dominant Follicle	
Previous (Baseline) cycle	9mm on 16 th day
Treatment cycle	12*10mm on 14 th Day
Follicle Rupture	
Previous(Baseline) cycle	18 th day
Treatment cycle	16 th day

DISCUSSIONS

Limitation

- There is a good scope for the study to be carried out on large samples for a conclusive result.
- Other *Prajasthapana Dravyas* to be involved in further studies.
- Further study can be carried out taking various endometrial disorders.
- Whether the exposure to a large number of assisted reproduction procedures can lead to more health issues.

Relevant Literature Discussion

Implantation^[9]

Male and female having normalcy of *dhatu*s reproductive age copulate, the unvitiated *shukra* is then ejaculated in a healthy *yoni marga*, the *sukra* reaches the *garbhashaya* and unites with the *suddha artava* resulting in conception. All factors concerned to conception can be

clubbed under; *Rutu*(Reproductive age), *Kshetra*(Female reproductive tract), *Ambu* (Required Nutrition and *Beeja* (Healthy Sperm; Ovum)

Fertilization^[10]

Fertilization is a process of the fusion of spermatozoa with the mature ovum. Almost always the fertilization occurs in the ampullary part of the fallopian tube. The, ovum, is picked up by the fimbriae which partly envelope the ovary especially at the time ovulation. Implantation is a process defined by which an embryo attaches to uterine wall and first penetrates the epithelium and then circulatory system of mother to form placenta. In fertilization it is the single most important step in the management of infertility. Implantation occurs in the endometrium of the anterior or posterior wall of the body near the fundus on the 5th – 7th day after fertilization which corresponds to the 20th -22nd day of regular menstrual cycle. Few steps that are important in implantation are apposition, adhesion, penetration and invasion. Thus, for a successful implantation, the embryo must be at the blastocyst age of development and hormone dependent changes resulting in development of a short lived receptive endometrium must have occurred.

Sperm migration in the female reproductive tract^[11,12]

This stage can be divided into four 4 steps and can be correlated with *matruja bhava* (maternal qualities) and *pitruja bhava* (Paternal Qualities) i.e Capacitation, acrosomal reaction, ZP penetration and fusion.

Importance of Pinopodes in Implantation^[13]

They are the accurate markers of the implantation window. They appear when the progesterone level is high in the luteal phase of menstrual cycle. They last for 2 days in all cases and their timings of their formation depends both on the hormone treatment applied and on the patients individual response

Prajasthapana Karma (Trans Urethral Procedure)^[14]

It's said as the drugs which eliminate defects and thus return embryo are as *prajastapana* (147) and effect of these drugs on the body is known as *prajasthapana karma*. *Prajasthapana* drugs are usually *kashaya*, *madhura*, *sinigdha*, *sheeta* and *balya*. Moreover, use of this drugs before conception promotes fertility and after conception gives strength to the uterus, stabilizes the foetus, helps normal development, prevents premature abortion and nourishes both, mother and child.

Niruha Basti (Enema Therapy)^[15]

Balaguduchyadi niruha basti is said to have the property of *sarvagada pramathi*. It is *jeevaniya* and *brumhaniya*.

Uttara Basti^[16,17]

It can be defined as the *basti* which is given through the *uttara marga* i.e through urethra or vagina. *Uttara basti* can be administered in two ways; *Mutrashayagata* (urinary tract) and *apathyamargata* (vagina). *Uttara basti* is said to be administered during the ovulating period.

Discussion on drugs***Shatavari Ghrita***^[18]

Shatavari having a similar chemical structure to that of estrogen plays an highly significant role in conception thus essential for reproduction. Moreover, this phytoestrogens help and support the normal hormone secretion level in female by showing and exerting estrogen like effect. Infertility, leads to increase stress factor thus *Shatavari* that contains Steroidal Saponins have glucocorticoid thus responsible for reducing the stress and help body adapt HcG stimulation can be related as having the same properties as *Shatavari Ghrita*, thus endometrial thickness is an important factor for implantation and appreciable increase in endometrial thickness found without any hormonal intervention. *Shatavari* which was used as the main drug is a *rasayana* considered under the *prajasthapana gana* and bear the antioxytoic, antiabortifacient and estrogenic property by which it acts as phytoestrogen and increased the thickness hence helps enhancing the quality of endometrium leading to increase the endometrial receptivity. *Prajasthapaka dravyas* are usually *kashaya*, *madhura*, *snigdha*, *sheeta* and *balya*. Use of these drugs before conception promotes fertility and after conception gives strength to the uterus, stabilizes the foetus, helps noral development, prevents premature abortion and nourishes both, mother and child Mode of action of *Uttara Basti*.^[19,20,21]

The mode of action can be divided into local effect and systemic effect. According to the site of action the drugs selection will depend. The *uttara basti* if administered in cervical canal than it will mainly act on cervical factors. Due to *katu* (pungent) and *usna* (Hot in Potency) *taila* (oil) that helps in the secretions of mucus from cervical glans. Intra vaginal administration helps in removal of infections with the drugs possessing anti bacterial properties.

Discussion on Shamana Drugs

Drugs like *Kanchanara Guggulu* has contents like *Guggulu* (*Commiphora mukul* Hook. ex Stocks.) is analgesic and anti-inflammatory. *Guggulu* contains the elements *Laghu* (light), *Ruksha* (dry), *Tikshna* (sharp), *Vishada* (clear), *Dipana* (stomachic enkindle the digestive fire), *Anulomana* (agents removing *Dosha* in a downward direction), and *Lekhana* (scraping) properties. Furthermore, it has *Medohara*, *Kapha Daurgandhya Hara*, *Hrudya* (cardio protective), and *Raktaprasadana* (blood purifying agents) properties and is useful in *Sthaulya* (obesity), *Prameha* (diabetes), and other diseases associated with *Sthaulya* (obesity). It has been reported that the mode of action is through modification of reproductive system and thyroid gland functions. *Kanchanara*, *Triphala*, and *Trikatu* are powerful decongestants that are combined with *Guggulu* to break down and eliminate hardened *Kapha*. This detoxifying blend promotes the proper function of the lymphatic and digestive systems, assisting in the prevention of further *Kapha* accumulation. *Kanchanara Guggulu* supports proper lymphatic function and balances *Kapha Dosha*, and promotes elimination of inflammatory toxins; it is alterative, anti-inflammatory, and tonic, and is used in cysts, malignant ulcers, syphilis, fistula, scrofula, sinus, and other conditions. *Arogyavartini Vati* that contains drugs It contains *Picrorrhiza kurroa* (*Kutki*), *Terminalia chebula* (*Haritaki*), *Terminalia bellerica* (*Bibhitaka*), *Embllica officinalis* (*Amalaki*), *Asphaltum* (*Silajatu*), *Commiphora wightii* (*Guggulu*), *Ricinus communis* (*Eranda*), *A Gandhaka suddha* (detoxified sulphur), *Tamra* (copper). This works to control the *vata gati* and thus remove obstructions in the *srotas*. It also acts on muscle tissues to give *bala* (strength and growth) that might have helped in improving the endometrial thickness.

Rationale of Conclusion

The result of this unique case study showed highly significant result. It is evident that the success rate of IUI an IVF are very less and implantation is the main factor responsible for threatment failure. Various factors are essential for the process of implantation and among them, functionally, the endometrial receptivity should be healthy, productive and bear the proper linings i.e. thickness to ensure implantation with health progeny.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, this case report shows the effectiveness of *Uttara Basti* in secondary infertility. With the help of *ayurveda* intervention, treatment efficacy can be increased. Hence,

significant improvement in conception indicates that *Uttara Basti* enhances conception rates and improve endometrial thickness.

Patients Perspective on Treatment Received

Before coming to *Ayurveda* I was very depressed and had tried many places to seek better treatment. I was already diagnosed with infertility but there were so much failure of conception even after IVF and IUI. Then I decided to take treatment in *ayurveda*. The first initial days of treatment were really hard and new to me but after so much patience and treatment protocols I finally conceived, and currently, I am feeling happy about the treatment I received.

Patient Consent

Informed written consent has been given by the patient for publishing this case study.

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